

ON THE ISSUE OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF TRANSLATION OF ENGLISH EXTENDED SENTENCES INTO RUSSIAN

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the current problem of improving the quality of translation of English sentences. The purpose of the article is to develop an effective model of strategies for translating English extended sentences into Russian. Research methods: analysis of scientific literature, induction, deduction, complex analysis and modeling. The article's author has developed a model of translation strategies, which includes the following translation strategies: literal translation, specification, generalization, antonymic translation, compensation and modulation. Translation strategies are selected depending on the presence or absence of set expressions in the Russian language, which allow for the accurate conveyance of the content of the text, the author's style and intent, and can also be considered equivalent in English.

Keywords: English extended sentences, translation into Russian, model of translation strategies, literal translation, specification, generalization, antonymic translation, compensation, modulation

INTRODUCTION

The principal parts of a sentence are the subject and the predicate, which form the grammatical basis of the sentence. In English, there are simple and complex subject and predicate constructions. The analysis of translation methods and techniques described in scientific literature [14, p. 172; 15, p. 216-222; 16, p. 352] allowed us to develop our own model of translation strategies, which, in our opinion, are most effective in translating extended principal and subordinate members of English sentences. This model includes the following strategies: syntactic assimilation or literal translation, specification, generalization, antonymic translation, compensation and modulation (semantic development). Let us first consider examples of translating extended principal members of an English sentence into Russian using the model we have presented. An example of translating an extended subject using syntactic assimilation (literal translation): «Playing on the nerves is the best he can» [8]. - «Игра на нервах – это лучшее, что он умеет». An example of translation of an extended predicate

by means of antonymic translation: «He evidently wished to return to his cabinet» [6]. — «Ему явно не терпелось вернуться к себе в кабинет». An example of translation of an extended subject by means of generalization: «Russia, Belarus, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan met to discuss work plans for 2013» [13]. – «Страны Евразийского экономического пространства встретились обсудить рабочие планы на 2013». An example of translating an extended predicate through modulation (semantic development): «Will plummeting oil prices succeed in reining in Vladimir Putin’s aggressive foreign policy where Western diplomacy and economic sanctions have so far failed?» [12]. – «Сумеют ли падающие нефтяные цены обуздать агрессивную внешнюю политику Владимира Путина, что пока не удается сделать западной дипломатии и экономическим санкциям?».

Subordinate members of a sentence serve to explain the principal ones and may have subordinate members that explain them. In English, there are definitions, additions, adverbial modifiers, and other subordinate members of a sentence. When translating extended subordinate members of English sentences, the same model of translation strategies presented above is applicable as when translating extended principal members of a sentence. Each case of translation is unique, so we can only indicate the trends in changes in the expansion of the principal and subordinate members of English sentences when translating them into Russian, but the quality of the translation is determined by the level of skill and creativity of the translator. An example of translating an extended addition by specifying: «The rain came in torrents» [3]. – «Полил сильный дождь». This addition in English was clarified by using the adjective “strong”. An example of translating an extended addition by generalization: «This is why America is comfortable with holding «World Series» and «World Championships» in which only Americans participate, as is the case with American football and baseball» [2]. – «Именно поэтому в Америке так популярны чемпионаты мира, где участвуют только американцы, как в случае с американским футболом или бейсболом». In this case, when translating the sentence into Russian, the names of the competitions, taking into account Russian realities, were generalized into a single term understandable to native speakers: “world championships”. Otherwise, additional explanations would have been required about how one type of competition differs from another. An example of translating an extended numeral using antonymic translation: «Not many people want to be cured» [9]. – «Мало, кто соглашается на лечение». In this case, the antonymic translation helped to adapt the idea for a Russian-speaking reader. The phrase «Немногие люди хотят вылечиться» would sound strange in Russian, since it is clear that all people want to be healthy. However, the phrase «Мало, кто соглашается на лечение» implies that people doubt the need for treatment and/or its quality, and therefore do not agree.

There is an extensive classification of predicate complication types, all the formulas we have studied are distinguished by the stability of the structure, preserving the harmony of the language and the precision of expressions. When translating, it is important to master all types of predicate complications. Let us consider the possibilities of using different strategies for translating predicate complication using specific examples: «During the press conference, Boris Johnson urged people to follow the latest rules to stop hospitals becoming overwhelmed with coronavirus patients» [7]. - «Во время пресс-конференции Борис Джонсон призвал людей следовать последним правилам, чтобы предотвратить переполнение больниц пациентами с коронавирусом» (literal translation); «He told me to come right over, if I felt like it». – «Сказал, хоть сейчас приходите, если надо» (specification); «Wouldn’t you like a cup of hot chocolate before you go?» [12]. — «Выпьешь чашку

горячего шоколада на дорогу?» (generalization); «Joe Biden didn't say anything» [5]. — «Джо Байден промолчал» (antonymous translation); «Well done!» [7] — «Браво! Молодец!» (compensation); «That was just a state that if we would have gotten it, it would have been nice. Arizona. But there's a possibility, maybe even a good possibility» [5]. — «Это был штат, получить который было бы прекрасно. Аризона. Есть такая вероятность, может быть, даже хорошая возможность» (modulation).

The complication of members of an English sentence can also be ensured by constructions of a complex complement, a complex subject and by means of the method of isolation. All types of expansion of members of a sentence from English can be translated by means of the translation strategies described above. Let us consider the possibilities of using different translation strategies for the complication of other members of a sentence using specific examples: «Great Britain makes other EU states accept unprofitable for them conditions» [11]. — «Великобритания заставляет другие страны ЕС принять невыгодные для них условия» (translation of a complex complement by means of syntactic assimilation); «Donald Trump is expected to fail soon» [10] - «Ожидается, что Дональд Трамп скоро потерпит неудачу на выборах» (translation of a complex subject by means of specification); «Democrats do not want and do not expect their voters to be aggressive in the streets, smashing shop windows and burning American flags» [4]. — «Демократы не хотят, чтобы их избиратели вели себя на улицах агрессивно и незаконно» (translation of a complex complement by means of generalization); «He is known to be not doing wrong things» [4]. — «Известно, что он всегда действует правильно» (the complex subject is rendered by an antonymic translation); «They saw their candidate preparing for the real fight» [12]. — «Они видели, что их кандидат реально собирается сражаться до последнего» (translation of a complex addition by means of compensation); «Bill Clinton, sitting on the chair in the first row, was indifferent to the audience» [1]. — «Билл Клинтон, приглашенный на мероприятие, был совершенно равнодушен к аудитории» (translation of isolation by modulation).

Thus, in the process of translating English sentences with the expansion and complication of the principal and subordinate members into Russian, as a rule, it becomes possible to preserve their syntactic constructions. At the same time, it is always important to take into account the existing differences in the grammar of the English and Russian languages, so each case is unique for the translator and requires the use of certain translation transformations. In order to improve the efficiency of translating English extended sentences into Russian, we have developed a model of translation strategies that includes the following strategies: syntactic assimilation or literal translation, specification, generalization, antonymous translation, compensation and modulation or semantic development. Certain translation strategies in the model are selected depending on the presence or absence of stable expressions in the Russian language, which allow for the accurate transmission of the content of the text and the author's style and intent, and can also be considered equivalents in English. It is often necessary to change the sentence structures, especially if the strategies of antonymous translation, specification, generalization, compensation and modulation are used.

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